

Kinetics of formation of 4-thiazolidinones by cyclocondensation reaction of Schiff bases and thioglycolic acid

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Kinetics of formation of 4-thiazolidinone by cyclocondensation of Schiff bases (SB) and thioglycolic acid (TGA) have been studied. The reaction shows first order dependence both on SB and TGA concentrations; it follows an overall second order kinetics. The reaction is catalyzed by toluene-4-sulfonic acid (TSA). The influence of a neutral salt, namely, sodium perchlorate, dielectric constant and temperature on the rate of reaction has been studied. Thermodynamic and kinetic parameters are evaluated. The order of reactivity of substituted SB is explained. A suitable mechanism is proposed. The activation parameters are consistent with the proposed mechanism.

TGA and SB show many applications in synthetic, analytical and kinetic fields¹. These are used for the formation of 4-thiazolidinone. It finds industrial, pharmaceutical and biological uses². This method has its own importance regarding the formation of 2,3-disubstituted-4-thiazolidinones because of their anaesthetic, anticonvulsant, amoebicidal and hypnotic activities. In view of the wide applications associated with 2,3-disubstituted-4-thiazolidinone, it was thought worthwhile to undertake kinetic study of formation of 4-thiazolidinone.

The present communication deals with kinetic study of formation of 4-thiazolidinone by cyclocondensation of SB and TGA in presence of TSA as catalyst.

Results and Discussion

The second order rate constant (k) determined at different [TGA] or [SB] are nearly constant, which suggests that the reaction follows second order kinetics. The linear plots of $1/(a-x)$ vs time and $\log [(a-x)/(b-x)]$ vs time are linear and confirm the second order kinetics (Table 1).

The rate of the reaction increases with increase in concentration of any one of the reactants. The plots of log rate vs log [TGA] or log [SB] for various SB studied are linear with approximately unit slope. Thus the reaction shows first order dependence both on [TGA] and [SB]. The rate

of the reaction increases with increase in the concentration of TSA, indicating reaction to be acid-catalyzed. TSA also acts as dehydrating agent. An investigation of reaction rates at various proportions of acetic and formic acid shows that increase in the percentage of formic acid enhances the rate of reaction.

Table 1. Effect of variation of concentration of reactants on the rate constant (k) ($10^3 k$, $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) at 303.15 K

[SB]	[TGA]	R ₁ =NO ₂	NO ₂	NO ₂	NO ₂	NO ₂	Cl	H	OMe
mol dm^{-3}	mol dm^{-3}	R ₂ =OEt	OMe	Me	H	Cl	H	H	H
0.05	0.05	4.15	3.75	3.33	3.20	1.94	2.08	1.52	1.39
0.05	0.04	4.08	3.52	3.57	3.17	1.91	1.92	1.44	1.44
0.05	0.03	4.04	3.68	3.19	3.14	1.92	1.92	1.36	1.44
0.05	0.02	4.01	3.20	3.09	3.06	1.81	1.81	1.33	1.28
0.05	0.01	3.94	-	-	3.08	-	-	-	-
0.04	0.05	4.15	3.74	3.51	3.23	1.94	1.92	1.44	1.49
0.03	0.05	4.18	3.73	3.35	3.26	1.92	1.92	1.52	1.44
0.02	0.05	4.22	3.87	3.52	3.30	1.92	2.13	1.55	1.49
0.01	0.05	4.23	-	-	3.34	-	-	-	-

The plot of $\log k$ as a function of the dielectric constant of the medium is straight-line with negative slope. This indicates participation of similarly charged ions in the rate-determining step. This plot is also useful to calculate the distance between the centers of the two interacting ions and it is 3.86×10^{-9} m, which is comparable with the values for molecular reactions³.

The effect of ionic strength on the rate of reaction was studied by using a neutral salt namely, sodium perchlorate. The rate of reaction increases with increasing ionic strength. The plot of $\log k$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ is straight-line with positive slope, which also indicates participation of similarly

Note

charged ions in rate-determining step. Since the reaction is acid-catalyzed so both the ions must be positively charged. The reactions were studied at the temperatures 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K. The rate constants for the various SB were evaluated. The plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ is straight line.

The values of E_a , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger and frequency factors (Table 2) were evaluated from Arrhenius plots. The negative values of entropy of activation for all the reactions indicate that the rate is slower⁴, and it also indicates rigid transition state. Relatively small values of ΔH^\ddagger and the negative ΔS^\ddagger values are consistent with the reactions which generally proceed through highly organized transition state⁵. The negative values of ΔS^\ddagger and lower values of frequency factors also support that the reactions involve similarly charged ions. Nearly constant values of ΔG^\ddagger with relative changes in ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger indicate the similarity in the mechanism of the reactions leading to the formation of 4-thiazolidinone⁶.

Table 2. Rate constant at different temperatures and activation parameters of cyclocondensation reaction

Substituent		$10^3 k$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)				E_a	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger	Freq	Fact(A)
R ₁	R ₂	303	308	313	318K	kJ	kJ	J	kJ	$\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	
						mol^{-1}	mol^{-1}	mol^{-1}	mol^{-1}		
NO ₂	Oet	4.15	6.14	8.77	12.53	58.91	56.36	-103.55	87.74	5.81	10^7
NO ₂	Ome	3.75	5.72	8.38	12.11	61.78	59.24	-92.67	87.32	1.66	10^6
NO ₂	Me	3.33	5.24	7.16	11.24	64.62	62.08	-87.37	87.65	4.5	10^6
NO ₂	H	3.20	4.59	6.98	10.47	63.76	61.20	-87.78	87.80	3.05	10^6
NO ₂	Cl	1.94	3.49	5.36	8.67	79.00	76.46	-63.67	87.57	7.93	10^{10}
Cl	H	2.08	3.25	4.91	7.28	66.66	64.13	-81.47	88.81	6.37	10^6
H	H	1.52	1.85	2.48	3.20	41.99	39.45	-153.24	89.89	2.52	10^4
OMe	H	1.39	1.80	2.29	3.05	41.57	39.03	-167.68	89.84	2.02	10^4

The rate of cyclocondensation reaction depends on the nature of *para*-substituent in aromatic amine and benzyldene moiety. From the experimental study of various SB it was observed that rate of cyclocondensation reaction increases as the electron-donating power of the substituent at the *para*-position in aromatic amine moiety increases. On the other hand, for the same *para*-substituent in aromatic amine moiety the rate of cyclocondensation reaction increases as the electron-withdrawing power of the *para*-substituent in the benzyldene moiety increases.

On the basis of experimental data, the rate law could be proposed as follows :

The rate of the reaction is directly proportional to the concentration of complex formed in step (3)

$$\text{Rate} \propto [\text{complex}]$$

$$\text{Rate} = k_6 [\text{complex}] \quad (5)$$

$$k_5 [S_1H^+] [S_2H^+] = k_6 [\text{complex}]$$

$$\text{Therefore, Rate} = k_5 [S_1H^+] [S_2H^+] \quad (6)$$

by applying steady state conditions to the concentration of complex, which is formed in reaction (3) and removed in reaction (4).

$$\text{Rate of formation of complex} =$$

$$\text{Rate of removal of complex,}$$

$$k_5 [S_1H^+] [S_2H^+] = k_6 [\text{complex}]$$

$$[\text{complex}] = \frac{k_5}{k_6} [S_1H^+][S_2H^+] \quad (7)$$

By applying steady state condition to the $[S_1H^+]$,

$$k_1 [S_1][H^+] = k_2 [S_1H^+] + k_5 [S_1H^+][S_2H^+] = [S_1H^+] (k_2 + k_5 [S_2H^+])$$

$$[S_1H^+] = k_1 [S_1][H^+]/(k_2 + k_5[S_2H^+]) \quad (8)$$

$$[S_1H^+] = k_1 [S_1][H^+]/[k_2(1 + k_5/k_2 [S_2H^+])]$$

$(1 + k_5/k_2 [S_2H^+])$ is very large and neglected.

$$[S_1H^+] = k_1/k_2 [S_1][H^+] \quad (9)$$

Similarly,

$$[S_2H^+] = k_3/k_4 [S_2][H^+] \quad (10)$$

By substituting values of $[S_1H^+]$ and $[S_2H^+]$ in eqn. (6),

Rate of formation of complex =

$$[k_1 k_3 k_5 / k_2 k_4] [S_1][S_2][H^+]^2$$

$$\text{Rate} = K [SB][TGA][H^+]^2$$

The experimental kinetic results obey the proposed rate law, which indicates that the rate law is in agreement with the experimental observations.

Experimental

TGA (A.R., S.D. fine; 99% purity) solutions were standardized by using standardized solution of iodine (A.R.)⁷. Various SB were prepared in pure form. Their solutions were prepared in suitable solvents. TSA (A.R., Sisco make) was used as catalyst as such.

Kinetic experiments were carried out in a thermostatic water-bath in chloroform/acetic acid medium at temperatures 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K. The reaction was initiated by mixing solutions of TGA and SB in presence of TSA as catalyst. The progress of the reaction was followed by withdrawing aliquots of reaction mixture at known intervals of time and estimating the unreacted TGA iodometrically. The formation of product 4-thiazolidinone was confirmed by IR and NMR spectra.

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